

Impact of information security regulations on SMEs in Ecuador

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Summary

The impact of information security regulations on SMEs in Ecuador significantly affects their competitiveness, profitability, and sustainability. Implementing information security policies, procedures, and controls, and complying with regulations such as the Personal Data Protection Law, requires the allocation of financial and human resources, which is a challenge for many SMEs due to their limited budget and technical knowledge. Despite this, non-compliance can result in penalties and business losses, highlighting the importance of these measures to ensure information security and business continuity. The level of awareness about these regulations varies, and while some companies are investing in training and security technologies, many still face significant obstacles to fully adapting.

Keywords : Cybersecurity, SMEs, Security regulations, Ecuador.

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The growing importance of information security has driven the creation of regulatory frameworks in Ecuador that are becoming mandatory for small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs). These companies are particularly vulnerable to cyber threats due to their limited resources, which makes it difficult to implement robust information security systems. The Personal Data Protection Law has intensified the need to protect sensitive information, however, many SMEs in Ecuador face difficulties in aligning with international standards such as ISO/IEC 27001 due to the cost involved in compliance (Jácome et al., 2021).

In terms of compliance level, it has been observed that only a small percentage of SMEs adopt the necessary security measures. Recent studies indicate that lack of awareness and cost of implementation are major obstacles (Jaramillo et al., 2015). Many SMEs focus on short-term profitability and overlook long-term security risks, which increases their vulnerability to cyberattacks. Often, these companies do not prioritize investment in cybersecurity infrastructure such as firewalls, encryption tools and regular vulnerability assessments, thus contributing to these risks.

Lack of financial resources is a crucial factor affecting SME compliance with information security regulations. The cost of implementing infrastructure, technologies, and training employees can be prohibitive for smaller companies. As noted by several experts, the investment required to comply with regulations such as ISO/IEC 27001 or COBIT 5 may not yield immediately visible returns, discouraging some companies from pursuing comprehensive

security solutions (Jaramillo et al., 2015). This lack of investment represents a significant risk, as noncompliance can result in costly data breaches or regulatory sanctions, and negatively impact reputation and operations.

Cyberattacks in Ecuador have been on the rise, with SMEs often prime targets due to weaker security systems. One report noted that Ecuador experienced a 30% increase in cyberattacks during 2023 (Salazar, 2024). The nature of these attacks, which often target financial data or intellectual property, highlights the need for SMEs to implement more robust security protocols. However, the gap between awareness and action remains a persistent problem.

During the years 2023 and so far in 2024, the Attorney General's Office in Ecuador has reported a significant increase in the number of complaints related to computer crimes. There is a 68% increase in complaints for unauthorized access to computer systems and a 40% increase in complaints of attacks on the integrity of computer systems in the Attorney General's Office in the period between January and August 2023 compared to the same period in 2024 (Prosecutor's Office, 2024). Since the Comprehensive Organic Criminal Code (COIP) came into force in 2014, there has been a sustained growth in reports of crimes such as fraudulent appropriation by electronic means and unauthorized access to computer systems. The Integrated System of Fiscal Actions (SIAF) recorded a total of 10,393 complaints for fraudulent appropriation and 1,265 complaints for unauthorized access to systems between 2014 and 2023. This increase reflects the need to strengthen cybersecurity measures in the country, as more citizens and companies are being affected by these criminal activities (Salazar Méndez et al., 2021).

Culturally, many SMEs in Ecuador do not perceive cybersecurity as a priority. Studies show that although business owners are aware of the risks, they often fail to take adequate

measures to mitigate them. Participation in training programs and investments in technology remain low, further exacerbating the security vulnerabilities of these companies (Tixi-Janeta et al., 2023). Without a cultural shift towards prioritizing information security, SMEs will continue to face significant risks.

The regulatory landscape, while seeking to protect consumer data and ensure business continuity, also introduces challenges for SMEs. Ecuador's National Cybersecurity Strategy emphasizes the need for resilience and preparedness, but many SMEs are lagging behind in adopting its recommendations (Ministry of Telecommunications, 2022). Greater government support and economic, infrastructure and training incentives are needed to encourage greater regulatory compliance and enhanced cybersecurity.

In conclusion, while regulations seek to improve the security posture of SMEs, economic, cultural and technical barriers prevent full compliance. Strengthening awareness, providing financial assistance and fostering a security culture among SMEs are essential steps to ensure that these companies can protect their information assets and thrive in a market where technology is ahead of regulation.

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